

Lie Symmetries and Invariants of Beams

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Abstract: The Lie symmetries compose a powerful method to obtain groups of operations that can preserve the characteristics of the differential equation invariants, for example its solutions, based on the connection between the geometric relation of symmetries and differential equations. This method was developed by Sophus Lie, a Norwegian mathematician, which work presents algorithms to calculate the symmetries and the invariants associated to these symmetries, as also how to calculate new coordinates to simplify and to reduce the order of the differential equations. In this work the Lie symmetries were calculated to the problem of a static Euler-Bernoulli beam to find the invariants associated to these symmetries to transform and reduce the order of the ordinary equation using the new computed coordinates.

Keywords: Lie Symmetries, Invariants, Canonical Coordinates, Order Reduction, Euler-Bernoulli Beam

INTRODUCTION

The Lie symmetries and the Noether theorem

An ordinary differential equation of second order is given in the form (Olver 1986, Blumman & Kumei 1989, Basquerotto et al. 2018a,b):

$$\mathcal{F}(x, u, u', u'') = 0 \quad (1)$$

where x and u are respectively the independent and dependent variables and the derivatives with respect to x are denoted by $'$.

The Lie symmetries can be calculated, preserving the characteristics of equation, by means of the infinitesimal generator \mathcal{X} :

$$\mathcal{X} = \left\{ \begin{matrix} \xi \\ \eta \end{matrix} \right\} \cdot \left\{ \begin{matrix} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial u} \end{matrix} \right\} = \xi \frac{\partial}{\partial x} + \eta \frac{\partial}{\partial u} \quad (2)$$

where ξ and η are the infinitesimal functions. These functions, associated to the prolongations of first and second order to second order equation, leads to the Lie condition (Olver 1986, Blumman & Kumei 1989, Basquerotto et al. 2018a,b):

$$(\mathcal{U}'' + \mathcal{X})\mathcal{F} = 0 \Rightarrow (\mathcal{U}'' + \mathcal{X})\mathcal{F} = \xi \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}}{\partial x} + \eta \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}}{\partial u} + \beta^{(1)} \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}}{\partial u'} + \beta^{(2)} \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}}{\partial u''} = 0 \quad (3)$$

if this condition is satisfied, its possible to find the Lie symmetries associated with the differential equation. The operator \mathcal{U}'' associated to the order of the equation is given by:

$$\mathcal{U}'' = \beta^{(1)} \frac{\partial}{\partial u'} + \beta^{(2)} \frac{\partial}{\partial u''} \quad (4)$$

where $\beta^{(1)}$ is the first order prolongation:

$$\beta^{(1)} = \mathcal{D}_x(\eta) - u' \mathcal{D}_x(\xi) = \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial x} + \left(\frac{\partial \eta}{\partial u} - \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x} \right) u' - \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial u} (u')^2 \quad (5)$$

and $\beta^{(2)}$ the second order prolongation, made in the second order derivatives of u :

$$\begin{aligned} \beta^{(2)} = \mathcal{D}_x(\beta^{(1)}) - u'' \mathcal{D}_x(\xi) = \frac{\partial^2 \eta}{\partial x^2} + \left(2 \frac{\partial^2 \eta}{\partial x \partial u} - \frac{\partial^2 \xi}{\partial x^2} \right) u' + \\ \left(\frac{\partial^2 \eta}{\partial u^2} - 2 \frac{\partial^2 \xi}{\partial x \partial u} \right) (u')^2 - \frac{\partial^2 \xi}{\partial u^2} (u')^3 + \left(\frac{\partial \eta}{\partial u} - 2 \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x} \right) u'' - 3 \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial u} u' u'' \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where \mathcal{D}_x is the total derivative:

$$\mathcal{D}_x = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} + u' \frac{\partial}{\partial u} + u'' \frac{\partial}{\partial u'} \quad (7)$$

The symmetries also can be powerful tools to express laws of nature (Oliveri 2010). If the lagrangian \mathcal{L} of the system is known, it is possible to determine invariants, \mathcal{A} , as (Olver 1986, Mei 2000, Martins 1999):

$$\mathcal{A} = \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial u'} (u' \xi - \eta) - \mathcal{L} \xi = \text{Constant} \Rightarrow \frac{d}{dx} \mathcal{A} = 0 \quad (8)$$

To rewrite the equation in terms of the canonical coordinates \bar{u} and \bar{x} it is necessary that the following relation be satisfied (Silva Júnior 2016):

$$\begin{aligned}\chi_1(\bar{u}) &= \xi \frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial x} + \eta \frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial u} = 0 \\ \chi_2(\bar{x}) &= \xi \frac{\partial}{\partial x} + \eta \frac{\partial}{\partial u} = 1\end{aligned}\tag{9}$$

From the canonical coordinates we can obtain the variable $v(\bar{x})$ for order reduction (Silva Júnior 2016, Gilmore 2008):

$$v(\bar{x}) = \frac{d}{d\bar{x}}\bar{u}(\bar{x})\tag{10}$$

APPLICATION ON BEAMS

To illustrate the use of the Lie symmetries, the Euler-Bernoulli equation was used, with a triangular load, q , and flexural stiffness, EI , showed by Fig. 1.

Figure 1 – Statically Determined Beam

The elastic line equation of the section between $0 < x < l$ is given by:

$$EI \frac{d^2 u}{dx^2} - V_A x - \frac{qx^3}{3} = 0\tag{11}$$

where $u(x)$ the function of deflection and V_A the reaction at the point A.

Applying the Lie condition it is possible to obtain a system of determining equations, whose solution gives the infinitesimal functions ξ and η , associated to the infinitesimal generator of symmetry, as shown in Tab. 1.

Table 1 – Infinitesimal functions ξ and η

	ξ	η
χ_1	0	1
χ_2	0	x
χ_3	0	$60EIlu - 10V_A lx^3 + qx^5$
χ_4	$12EI\ell$	$6V_A lx^2 - qx^4$
χ_5	$12EI\ell x$	$6V_A lx^3 - qx^5$
χ_6	$15EI\ell x^2$	$x(-qx^5 + 5V_A lx^3 + 15EI\ell u)$
χ_7	$12(qx^5 - 10V_A lx^3 + 60EI\ell u)EI\ell$	$(qx^5 - 10V_A lx^3 + 60EI\ell u)(-qx^4 + 6V_A lx^2)$
χ_8	$15x(qx^5 - 10V_A lx^3 + 60EI\ell u)EI\ell$	$(qx^5 - 10V_A lx^3 + 60EI\ell u)(-qx^5 + 5V_A lx^3 + 15EI\ell u)$

By the Noether theorem the invariants associated to the Lie symmetries can be calculated. The lagrangian of the system is given by:

$$\mathcal{L} = - \int_0^x \frac{M(x)^2}{2EI} dx = \frac{1}{630EI\ell^2} [x^3 (5q^2 x^4 - 42V_A q\ell x^2 + 105V_A^2 \ell^2)]\tag{12}$$

Starting from the conservation law of the system, associated to the fourth invariant, the sum of bending moments at point B was obtained and was possible to calculate the reaction at the point A:

$$\frac{d}{dx} \mathcal{A}_4 = - \frac{2\ell^3}{3} (q\ell - 3V_A) = 0 \Rightarrow V_A = \frac{q\ell}{3}\tag{13}$$

From the canonical transformations and using the infinitesimal generators, it is possible to compute the the new variables that maintain invariant the differential equation. By using the fourth infinitesimal generator, \mathcal{X}_4 , its possible to obtain the following coordinates:

$$x_4 = \frac{1}{60EI\ell} \left(qx^5 - 10V_A \ell x^3 + 60u(x)EI\ell \right) \quad u_4 = \frac{x}{12EI\ell} \quad (14)$$

To reduce de order of the equation using the canonical coordinates it's important to define the new variable v_4 :

$$v_4 = \frac{d}{dx_4} u_4 = \frac{1}{qx^4 + 12EI\ell u'(x) - 6V_A \ell x^2} \quad (15)$$

and rewriting the equation (11) in terms of v_4 and x_4 it is possible to obtain the reduced-order equation and their solution:

$$\frac{d}{dx_4} v_4(x_4) = 0 \Rightarrow \mathcal{C} \quad (16)$$

where \mathcal{C} is a constant of integration.

It is important to note that even in the new variables the solution remains invariant, that is, returning to the original variables u and x and integrating once in dx the solution of the original equation is obtained:

$$u(x) = \frac{1}{12EI\ell} \left(-\frac{qx^5}{5} + 2V_A x^3 \ell + \frac{x}{\mathcal{C}_1} \right) + \mathcal{C}_2 \quad (17)$$

where \mathcal{C}_1 and \mathcal{C}_2 are constants of integration.

Although the problem treated is relatively simple and with a known solution, the Lie method is interesting because it allows more economical solutions of differential equations. It is important to note that the results obtained can also be described in a general way, as a function of any $M(x)$ at the elastic line equation.

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REFERENCES

- Basquerotto, C. H. C. C., Righetto, E. & da Silva, S. (2018a), 'Applications of the Lie Symmetries to Complete Solution of a Bead on a Rotating Wire Hoop', *Journal of the Brazilian Society of Mechanical Sciences and Engineering*.
- Basquerotto, C. H. C. C., Righetto, E. & da Silva, S. (2018b), 'As Simetrias de Lie de um Pião', *Revista Brasileira de Ensino de Física* **40**(2).
- Blumman, G. W. & Kumei, S. (1989), *Symmetries and Differential Equations*, Applied Mathematical Sciences 81, Springer, New York.
- Gilmore, R. (2008), Lie groups and differential equations, in C. U. Press, ed., 'Lie Groups, Physics, and Geometry', Cambridge University Press, pp. 284–308.
- Martins, A. S. (1999), 'Simetrias e Leis de Conservação na Mecânica Clássica', *Revista Brasileira de Ensino de Física* **21**, 33–39.
- Mei, F. X. (2000), 'Lie symmetries and conserved quantities of constrained mechanical systems', *Acta Mechanica* **141**(3), 135–148.
- Oliveri, F. (2010), 'Lie Symmetries of Differential Equations: Classical Results and Recent Contributions', *Symmetry* **2**(2), 658.
- Olver, P. J. (1986), *Applications of Lie groups to differential equations*, 107, 2nd edn, Springer US, New York.
- Silva Júnior, C. C. d. (2016), 'Simetrias de Lie de equações a derivadas fracionárias e íntegro-diferenciais'.

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